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Artificial Intelligence On Auditing Process In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the artificial intelligence on auditing process in Nigeria. The sub-objectives were to: determine the effect of task automation on auditing process in Nigeria; examined the effect of risk assessment on auditing process in Nigeria. Primary data for the study was questionnaire. The population of interest consists of all the employees of staff of commercial bank. However the total Number of staff in the selected bank is 397. This population figure was derived from human resources department of the selected banks (Zenith, Fidelity, UBA, First Bank. and GT bank) given the nature of this study, since the population is not up to 1000 respondents the research utilized the entire 397 population. Statistics, such as frequency count and percentages will be used in the analysis of personal characteristics, while hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis. The study found that, Task Automation has positive significant effect on auditing process, Risk assessment has positive significant effect on auditing process. The study concluded that artificial intelligence has positive significant effect on auditing process. The study recommended that Firms should deploy AI-based analytics and machine learning models that can identify unusual patterns, detect anomalies, and flag high-risk transactions more accurately. Auditors should integrate AI insights into their traditional risk assessment processes to enhance audit planning, materiality judgments, and risk prioritization

Keywords: artificial intelligence, auditing process, risk assessment, task automation

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly reshaping the auditing process in Nigeria's deposit money banks by automating complex tasks, enhancing data analysis, and improving the accuracy of audit judgments (Adeyemi, & Fagbemi, 2021). With banks generating large volumes of financial transactions daily, traditional audit methods often struggle to provide timely and comprehensive assurance. AI technologies such as task automation, risk assessment, and automated audit tools now enable auditors to process data faster, detect anomalies more effectively, and strengthen internal control evaluations (Akinadewo, 2021). In Nigerian deposit banks, the integration of AI into auditing has become essential for improving audit efficiency, reducing operational risks, and ensuring compliance in an environment characterized by rapid digital transformation and heightened regulatory expectations (Al-Rifai, 2022).. As a result, AI is emerging as a strategic tool that enhances audit quality and supports more reliable decision-making within the banking sector.

The quick development of information and communication technology (ICT), especially artificial intelligence, is reshaping audit practice. With the help of this revolutionary technology, audit procedures will be reorganized and audit opinions will be more accurate, efficient, and effective. Ghanoun and Alaba (2020) claim that as ICT tools advance in the modern corporate environment, more data is produced by companies. As a result, public accounting firms must keep up with this revolution by investing in state-of-the-art ICT tools to efficiently examine the massive amounts of financial data generated. AI techniques

and tools are essential to the development and expansion of audit practice. AI in audit is a combination of technologies that improve and change audit practice, according to Issa et al. (2016). Albawwat and AlFrijat (2021) assert that AI can facilitate data mining and pooling to improve audit procedures at different phases. According to Owonifari et al. (2023), AI structures offer the advantage of being able to create audit tests, write audit reports, and analyze entire sets of data. According to Kokina and Davenport (2017), data analytics and AI systems are especially well-suited to auditing. According to Noordin (2022), AI applications in audit practice are anticipated to include customer consulting, the provision of services like audit and fraud detection, and the enhancement of audit firms' internal procedures.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the artificial intelligence on auditing process in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- iv. To determine the effect of task automation on auditing process in Nigeria
- v. To examine the effect of risk assessment on auditing process in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Nussel and Norvig (2021) define AI through four potential goals: systems that think like humans, act like humans, think rationally, or act rationally. The study goes further to state that AI is the study of agents that receive percepts from the environment and perform actions. The EU's landmark regulatory framework (2023) defines AI as software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I [e.g., machine learning, logic-based systems] and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with. According to OECD (2023), an AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment. The broad field of creating machines or software capable of performing tasks that require intelligence when done by humans, while acknowledging that 'intelligence' itself remains an ill-defined and culturally contingent concept (Mitchell, 2023).

2.1.2 Auditing Process

The auditing process refers to the systematic and structured procedures carried out by auditors to obtain sufficient and reliable evidence about an organization's financial records, operations, or internal controls (Aigboduwa, & Awe, 2020). It involves an independent examination of financial statements and related activities to determine whether they present a true, fair, and accurate view of the entity's financial position. The auditing process follows recognized standards and consists of key stages such as planning the audit, assessing risks, evaluating internal controls, gathering evidence through testing, and forming an audit opinion (Akintoye, Aluko, & Abidoye, 2019). The core concept behind the auditing process is to enhance the credibility of financial information by ensuring transparency, accountability, and compliance with regulatory and professional requirements. By conducting an objective and evidence-based assessment, the auditing process helps detect errors, fraud, and irregularities while providing assurance to stakeholders including management, investors, regulators, and the public that the organization's financial reporting is reliable. In essence, the auditing process serves as a vital tool for promoting good governance, sound financial management, and trust in the financial system (Akinyemi, Obioma, Oyinlola, & Oloyede, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Classical Theory of Artificial Intelligence (CTAI)

The Classical Theory of Artificial Intelligence serves as the foundation for this research (CTAI). The theory was propounded in the year 1956 by Claude Shannon and Arthur Samuel. The theory, according to Muller (2012), is focused on the question of whether AI is even conceivable. It prompts inquiries like,

"Can a machine think?" and "Can a machine do x?" According to Dagunduro et al. (2023), AI will likely never completely replace human intelligence. However, Super Artificial Intelligence (SAI) machines, which were developed quickly, are in a serious race with Human inventors, according to Zohuri and Rahmani (2020). Thus, while this theory stands on the premix that humans will still provide the necessary transactions for AI to operate, it is still a matter of argument that several operations of humans have not been totally taken over by AI in the recent years. Despite the advancement in AI, however, this theory is still relevant as to the limitations of what machines can perform, asserting that AI is fundamentally limited and should be replaced with other methods (Muller, 2012; Omaliko et al., 2017). While this study focusses on the link between artificial intelligence and auditing practice, this theory creates more awareness as to the continued relevance of accountants on accounting activities but with dimensional changes in approach. Also, according to Omaliko and Okpala (2021), the classical theory of artificial intelligence provides a foundational lens to analyze AI adoption in auditing, emphasizing perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived easy use (PEOU) as critical drivers. Extensions incorporating trust, transparency, and regulatory alignment further refine its applicability. Addressing these factors through training, user centric design, and explain ability can enhance AI integration in auditing practices.

2.3 Empirical Study

Rita & Onuora, (2025) investigated the role of artificial intelligence (AI) on auditing practices in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between AI and audit practices, AI (independent variable) was proxy using expert system (ES) and deep learning machine (DLM) while audit practices was the dependent variable. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using least squares regression model operated with E-Views.12. Survey design was adopted and data for the study was obtained through e-questionnaire survey sent to the various Staff WhatsApp Group Platform of the selected audit firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The findings of the study indicate that expert system and deep learning machine have positive and significant effect on audit practices in Nigeria. Based on this, the study concludes that the use of AI in auditing ensures effective audit practices in Nigeria.

Appah (2025) investigates the moderating role of auditors' expertise and experience on the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) adoption and audit quality in audit firms in Nigeria. Grounded on Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory, a quantitative method was employed using data collected from a structured questionnaire administered to 237 respondents after validity and reliability tests. The structural equation modelling (SEM) shows a significantly positive relationship between expert systems of AI, neutral network of AI, machine learning of AI, fuzzy logic of AI, on audit quality of public audit firms in Nigeria, and a significantly positive relationship between auditors' expertise and experience on audit quality of public audit firms in

Nigeria. The study also revealed that auditors' expertise and experience moderate a significantly positive relationship between artificial intelligence (expert systems, neutral network, machine learning and fuzzy logic) on audit practice (audit quality) on audit quality of public audit firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the paper concludes that artificial intelligence is a significant determinant of audit quality in Nigeria. The findings suggest that auditors' expertise and experience significantly moderate the association between artificial intelligence as a significant determinant of audit quality of audit firms in Nigeria.

Saleh, Shaher and Zayed, (2021) examine the effect of artificial intelligence technologies on audit evidence, from the point of view of certified auditors in information technology (IT) companies in Jordan. The study was used a descriptive analytical approach. The data were collected from (314) auditors, using a questionnaire developed for this purpose.. The findings of the study showed that expert system had effect on the audit evidence. Neural network technology did not provide any significant effect on the audit evidence. The study recommended increased interest in artificial intelligence technologies by audit offices operating in Jordan because of its scientific importance in improving the collection of audit evidence.

Isaiah, Akintoye, Agugom, & Olagunju, (2023). examines the effect of artificial intelligence on audit quality by employing the survey method, using structured questionnaires administered to practicing accountants and staff of the Big Four accounting firms The Taro Yamani formula was used to determine the sample size, and a total of 641 questionnaires were retrieved. Cronbach's alpha was employed to test the reliability and validity alongside the pilot testing conducted. Descriptive statistics and inferential analysis were also used. The results of the descriptive method showed that many of the respondents support the usefulness of artificial intelligence. The regression results revealed that artificial intelligence has a positive effect on audit quality. Based on the results, it is recommended that managers and accountants in private, corporate, and accounting firms should embrace the application of artificial intelligence due to its economic value and helpful effect of improving audit quality in terms of accuracy, reliability, and timely financial reporting

Amos, Abiola Ibukun & Kayafat (2024) investigated how artificial intelligence (AI) affects the quality of audit judgement (QAJ). Seventy auditors from ten AI-integrating audit firms in Nigeria were selected using a stratified sampling strategy and the Taro Yamane formula as part of a quantitative study design. A standardised Likert-scale Google form questionnaire was used to gather data, and regression analysis was employed to assess the connections between AI and numerous aspects of audit judgement quality. According to the study, the accuracy and reliability of audit findings are much improved by AI (coefficient = 0.417, $p = .000$), and more accurate judgements result from more AI use. AI has no discernible impact on decision-making time, nevertheless (coefficient = 0.170, $p = 0.651$). Additionally, AI greatly enhanced auditors' perceived confidence in their assessments (coefficient = 0.481, $p = .000$) and their dependence on AI tools for suggestions (coefficient = 0.411, $p = .000$). The study comes to the conclusion that AI has a major and favourable impact on the QAJ. To ensure that auditors can utilise AI to improve the quality of audit judgements, the study suggests that audit firms invest in AI technologies and provide training in data analytics, AI and AI, bias identification, and the interpretation of AI-generated insights.

METHODOLOGY

The techniques for gathering, measuring, and analyzing data pertaining to the study's goals are all included in the research design. The survey method was selected as the research approach for this investigation. Since the researcher has no control over the factors or the result, the survey research approach is the most suitable. First-hand or raw data, original documents, and materials produced by participants or witnesses of the event or events being studied are examples of primary data. Questionnaires and in-person interviews will be utilized to collect primary data for the project. All commercial bank employees make up the population of interest. However, the organization employs 397 people in total. The human resources departments of the chosen banks (Zenith, Fidelity, UBA, First Bank, and GT Bank) provided this population number. Due to the nature of the study, the research included all 397 respondents because the population did not reach 1000. The significance threshold of 0.05 was used to test the hypotheses. Regression analysis and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) were used in this research.

RESULT INTERPRETATION

4.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		
1	.673 ^a	.524	.513	.96254	.224	20.844	4	365	.000	1.820

a. Predictors: (Constant), TKA, RKA

b. Dependent Variable: ADP

Table 4.1.1 shows that R² co-efficient of determination which measures the strength of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable has the value of 0.52. This implies that 52% of the variation in auditing process is explained by variations in task automation and risk assessment. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.51%. Test for autocorrelation: This is used to test whether errors corresponding to different observations are uncorrelated. If the value of the Durbin-Watson from the regression result is close to 2 no multicollinearity in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is a problem of multicollinearity. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 2 reveals no multicollinearity in the model. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.820 which indicates that the study is free from the problems of multicollinearity.

Table 4.1.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	308.738	4	19.311	20.844	.000 ^b
	Residual	246.261	365	.926		
	Total	554.998	369			

a. Dependent Variable: ADP

b. Predictors: (Constant), TKA, RKA

The f-statistics value of 20.844 in table 4.1.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables have significant effect on dependent variable and can collectively explain the variations in artificial intelligence variables on auditing process. The F-test of 20.844 indicates that the regression model is statistically significant. This implies that the explanatory variables jointly have a significant effect on the dependent variable

Table 4.1.3. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.467	.413		5.967	.000	1.655	3.279
	TKA	.116	.081	.124	2.438	.001	.274	.042
	RKA	.285	.100	.270	2.851	.005	.482	.089

a. Dependent Variable: ADP

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing accounting theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the accounting parameter under review. In table 4.1.3 above, we found out that task automation has a positive sign given its value as .116; this implies that a unit increase in task automation increases the auditing process by 11%, this conform to theoretical expectation. Risk assessment has a positive sign given its value as .0.285; this implies that a unit increase in Risk assessment increases the auditing process by 28%, this conform to theoretical expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of the explanatory parameters in the model. From table t-test above task automation is 2.438 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it has contributed significantly to auditing process. Risk assessment is 2.851 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to auditing process at 5% level of significant.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Task Automation has no positive significant effect on auditing process.

Task Automation has a t-statistics of 2.438 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state that Task Automation has positive significant effect on auditing process.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Risk assessment has no positive significant effect on auditing process.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Risk assessment has a t-statistics of 2.851 and a probability value of 0.005 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Risk assessment has positive significant effect on auditing process

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that artificial intelligence (AI) plays a transformative role in enhancing the auditing process in Nigeria. The findings show that AI-driven task automation has a positive and significant effect on audit efficiency by reducing manual workload, minimizing human errors, and accelerating the execution of repetitive audit procedures. Similarly, AI-based risk assessment demonstrates a significant effect on the auditing process by improving auditors' ability to detect anomalies, identify high-risk transactions, and strengthen the overall quality of audit judgments. Taken together, these results indicate that the integration of AI technologies substantially enhances audit reliability, timeliness, and decision-making. Therefore, Nigerian audit firms that adopt AI tools are better positioned to achieve higher audit effectiveness and maintain competitiveness in the evolving digital audit environment. Audit firms in Nigeria should invest in AI-based tools that automate repetitive tasks such as data extraction, validation, vouching, and reconciliations to increase audit speed and reduce errors. Auditors should be trained regularly on how to use automated systems, interpret AI-generated outputs, and integrate automated procedures into traditional audit workflows. Firms should deploy AI-based analytics and machine learning models that can identify unusual patterns, detect anomalies, and flag high-risk transactions more accurately. Auditors should integrate AI insights into their traditional risk assessment processes to enhance audit planning, materiality judgments, and risk prioritization.

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